

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: TALEMWA****FIRST NAME: MICHAEL****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanicsThe author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 15%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE DSDD ACA-401D

1. The structure of an excellent academic essay should have the following parts.
 - Introduction, literature review, methodology
 - Introduction, body, conclusion¹**
 - Abstract, introduction, literature review
 - Abstract, introduction, methodology
2. It is a means of documenting a writer's approach to some aspects of writing and enhances consistency.
 - Word editor
 - Writing style
 - Style guide²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*. Fourth ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 10.

² Ibid., 41.

- Academic essay
- 3. In conducting research, the best questions are those whose answers;
 - Are new to the field of study
 - Are straight forward
 - Raise several more questions³**
 - Are agreeable to everybody
- 4. One of the worst mistakes a researcher can make, intended or unintended, is
 - Practicing plagiarism⁴**
 - Having few references
 - Applying a wrong style
 - Not being consistent
- 5. The two citation styles used in academic writing include
 - Notes-author, bibliographical-date styles
 - Bibliographical-author, bibliographical-date styles
 - Parenthetical, footnote-endnote styles
 - Notes-bibliographical, author-date styles⁵**
- 6. Quotation marks must be used for any quoted material in a paper, irrespective of the length of the quotation.
 - True
 - Untrue⁶**

³ Turabian, Kate L., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 20.

⁴ Ibid., 77.

⁵ Ibid., 141.

⁶ Ibid., 371.

- Sometimes
 - Always
7. Critical components of a study that must feature in the introduction include
- Problem, purpose, research questions
 - Problem, purpose, rationale
 - Problem, purpose, research questions, rationale⁷**
 - Problem, purpose, rationale, research design
8. One of the significant challenges in conducting research is
- Having access to the required resources
 - Getting a good supervisor
 - Convincing participants to take part in the study
 - Identifying a sound, researchable topic⁸**
9. When writing statics where two or more numbers are used, a writer should always use
- Words
 - Figures⁹**
 - Numerals
 - Both figures and words
10. According to the European Commission, while writing footnotes
- Begin with a capital letter and end with a full stop¹⁰**

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 75.

⁸ Ibid., 98.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: Eight Edition* (European Commission, 2021), 37.

¹⁰ Ibid., 62.

- Place a coma after the first word
- Make the entire text bold
- Italicize the entire text

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

European Commission. *English Style Guide*. Eight Edition, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. The University of Chicago Press: Chicago, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.